

Thematic workshop proposal I-RIM 3D 2025

1. Workshop Title

Human-robot augmentation: a user-centered perspective

2. Organizers

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3. Workshop Format

Format. The idea is to have a workshop that revolves around a hands-on demonstration of human-robot augmentation which will be performed by a potential end-user of the system. In particular, a post-stroke patient will take part in the workshop, perform the demo, and share his thoughts on augmentation. The demo will then also be available for the speakers to try. After the demo, the invited speakers will be asked to contextualize how robotic augmentation relates to their research field and share their thoughts on the demonstration.

Demo. A post-stroke patient with an impaired upper limb will control a supernumerary robotic arm placed on a table thanks to a wearable sensorimotor interface. Bimanual tasks requiring the coordination between human and artificial limbs will be performed.

Tentative schedule:

Event	Timing	Activity
Workshop (90 min)	10 min	<u>Workshop introduction</u> (D. Prattichizzo)
	20 min	<u>Demo with an end-user</u> . Invited end-user: A. Bondi; demo presenter: B. Brogi
	60 min	<u>Speaker's presentations (10 min each) and Panel Discussion:</u> Moderators: D. Prattichizzo, M. Malvezzi, G. Salvietti Panelists: A. D'Avella, T. Asfour, L. Zollo
Poster Session (60 min)	15 min	Flash talks
	45 min	Poster session with extended abstracts

4. Workshop Objectives and Main Topics

The idea of augmenting manipulation or locomotion capabilities of humans through supernumerary robotic limbs (SRLs) is potentially disruptive in the field of human-robot interaction. SRLs find the most pressing application in the support of people with motor disabilities, to let them recover lost motor functions. SRLs development, however, is still in its infancy, as these robots pose several design and control challenges. In addition, a lot has to be done in terms of overcoming non-technical barriers that prevent the adoption of such robots, including ethical, legal, and socio-economical aspects). In this context, having a user-centered and multidisciplinary point of view on the problem is paramount. In this workshop, we will ask top scientists in their fields to discuss together a live demo performed with a post-stroke patient controlling a supernumerary robotic arm which augments his manipulation capabilities. The discussion will be guided by fundamental questions in augmentative robotics, such as: Is it possible to perceive SRLs as a part of our own body? At which stage of technology development do end-users need to be involved in the design of SRLs? Will humans be able to simultaneously control artificial and natural limbs? Can end-users perceive supernumerary limbs as extensions of their own body even if the supernumerary limb is not wearable?

5. Keywords

Human-robot augmentation, User-centered design, Sensorimotor Interfaces, Assistive Robotics

6. Preferred Date

The preferred date is Friday 17th, 2025.

7. List of Speakers

Andrea D’Avella, Fondazione Santa Lucia, Roma (confirmed)

Tamim Asfour, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (confirmed)

Loredana Zollo, Università Campus Bio-Medico di Roma (confirmed)

Alessandro Bondi, Azienda USL Toscana Sud Est, Siena (confirmed)

Bernardo Brogi, University of Siena (confirmed)

8. Expected Number of Attendees

Based on similar previous events we expect 20-25 participants in the workshop.

9. Target Audience

The proposed workshop aims at demonstrating some of the latest results in the field of human-robot augmentation. The user-centered and hands-on focus makes the workshop interesting both for experts in the field of human-centered robotics and for stakeholders related to the envisaged assistive application, from potential end-users (people with upper limb disabilities) to neurologists and healthcare professionals.

10. Workshop Outcomes

Upon speakers’ approval, we will include their presentations in the workshop website, where we will also include the list of I-RIM papers presented in the workshop, with a link to the I-RIM proceedings. In addition, we plan to prepare a similar workshop proposal to be submitted to IEEE ICRA 2026. If both I-RIM and ICRA workshops are successful in terms of participation and audience involvement, we will plan a special issue on user-centered robotic augmentation in one of the most important journals in robotics (e.g., IEEE TRO, RAL, RAM). Organizers already have experience in proposing and handling special issues in major venues.

11. Plan for Special Issue or Session

As stated above, based on the outcomes of the I-RIM and ICRA workshops, we will plan a special issue in one of the most important journals in robotics (e.g., IEEE TRO, RAL, RAM), encouraging the submission also from the poster presenters who participated in the workshops.

12. Call for Extended Abstracts

To encourage the submission of I-RIM contributions related to robotic augmentation and promote the participation of young students, we will open a call for papers of the workshop encouraging interested authors to choose our workshop as a venue for poster presentation directly during the submission of their contributions through the I-RIM 3D submission system on EasyChair. We will keep the same deadline as the conference. The call for posters and participation will be published on the workshop website and it will be spread through all the different communication channels (e.g., mailing lists, social networks). During a flask talk presentation, just before the posters session, presenters will have time to briefly pitch their work. In addition to the official workshop website, the related news will be published on the organizers’ social networks profiles (e.g., LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram).

13. Workshop Webpage

<https://sites.google.com/unisi.it/irim25-ws-robotic-augmentation>

14. Notes on Registration

Currently, we plan to use the 2 free one-day registrations for A. Bondi, who is a post-stroke patient, and A. D’Avella, who is a neurophysiologist and probably wouldn’t otherwise participate in the I-RIM conference.